

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B200
Date: 18 May 2006
Take Off: 09:31:44
Landing: 14:20:27
Flight Time: 4h48m43s

Campaign: ICEPIC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	Mission Scientist 2	Alan Blyth	Leeds University
8	CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
9	Mission Scientist training	Chris Taylor	CEH
10	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office
11	CCN	Richard Cotton	Met Office
12	Core Chem / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B200 Track 18-MAY-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b200
 Date: 18 May 2006
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: SW

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
090052		INU	0.52 kft	126	to nav
091902		heimann	0.52 kft	126	cal 15
093144		T/O	0.51 kft	212	Cranfield
093740		ASP	9.1 kft	243	open
093828		twc	9.0 kft	241	check ok
093915		DI - NDI	9.0 kft	240	check ok
094735		!	9.1 kft	243	Nev & JW indicate 0 o n derived data
094754		!	9.7 kft	251	drs data ok
094811		!	10.1 kft	254	derived airspeed 0
094826		!	10.5 kft	255	port aft reset - all ok
095006		JW	13.7 kft	249	zero
095028		NEV	14.4 kft	249	zero
095225		JW	17.7 kft	249	zero
095446		TWC	20.0 kft	250	status @ -25C, fl200
100508		Video	20.0 kft	234	#1 ffc #2 rfc
101148	102358	Profile 1.0	20.0 - 8.6 kft	230	
102650	102951	Profile 1.1	8.6 - 5.5 kft	341	
102741		JW	7.7 kft	334	zero
102753		nev	7.5 kft	333	zero
103112	103813	Profile 1.2	5.5 - 0.24 kft	209	
104355	105323	Run 1.0	1.6 - 1.7 kft	053	500ft under cloudbase
105507	110508	Run 1.1	1.7 kft	265	
105652		heimann	1.7 kft	269	cal 10
111228	111930	Run 2.0	7.0 kft	048	
111643		nev	7.0 kft	044	total water alarm
112229	113441	Run 3.0	8.0 kft	272	
113725	114720	Run 4.0	9.0 - 9.1 kft	333	
114306		Video	9.0 kft	073	#3 ffc #4 ffc
114803	120548	Run 5.0	10.1 - 10.0 kft	261	
115221		!	10.1 kft	234	DI heater on
120149		Video	10.0 kft	205	ffc iced
120654	121136	Profile 2.0	10.0 - 5.2 kft	291	
121021		!	6.5 kft	291	DI heater off
121305	121447	Profile 2.1	5.3 - 3.7 kft	120	qnh 1006
121511	121650	Profile 2.2	3.6 - 1.7 kft	153	
121749	123009	Run 6.0	1.7 kft	089	qnh 1006
123241	124457	Run 7.0	7.0 kft	299	
124349		!	7.0 kft	197	DI failed
124914	130805	Run 8.0	11.0 kft	036	
125245		!	11.0 kft	013	nev tw back on line
125954		JW	11.0 kft	063	zero
130012		nev	11.0 kft	064	zero
130311		!	11.0 kft	096	ffc obscured
131002	131932	Run 9.0	11.0 kft	091	
131259		Video	11.0 kft	078	#5ffc #6rfc
131924		!	11.0 kft	077	overhead Chilbolton
132358	132710	Profile 3.0	11.0 - 7.0 kft	267	
132710	134237	Run 10.0	7.0 kft	245	
133010		!	7.0 kft	255	14.2 m from Chilbolto
134510	135514	Run 11.0	7.0 kft	102	
142027		Land	0.55 kft	211	Cranfield
142723		gps	0.57 kft	309	52'04.36N 0'37.50W
143004		inu	0.57 kft	309	52' 01.60N 0' 38.60W

B200 Track 18-MAY-06

Flight No: B200

Date: 18th May 2006

Trial objectives:

To investigate the development of ice-phase and precipitation in Cu over the UK.

Location:

In developing Cu clouds over SW / Central S.England or Wales (suggest a rectangular box with NW corner at 54deg N, 06deg W and SE corner at 50deg N, 01deg W), or alternatively over E. England.

Weather:

Either individual, or groups of Cu cloud forming predominantly over land. Evolving clouds may also be tracked over the sea.

Special requirements:

Key temperature levels for cloud penetrations are 0, -3, -6, -9C then colder as reqd. If operating near Chilbolton radar, relay range/bearing of target clouds to "Radsearch" (130.575 MHz). Maintain continuous monitoring of turbulence probe differential pressures – if any icing observed, descend below freezing level to clear.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 10:00L.
2. Transit to the operating region at FL200 and identify suitable clouds (40mins).
3. Perform profile descent from FL200 to minimum permitted altitude at 1000ft/minute (70mins). May be stepped to avoid cloud penetrations. Profile ideally finishes below target clouds.
4. Perform a SLR below cloud for 10minutes in a direction determined by the mission scientist to remain in inflow of target clouds (85mins).
5. Turn onto reciprocal heading and perform a SLR at 500ft below cloudbase for ten minutes (100mins).
6. Ascend to around the 0C level or 500ft below the cloud top (110mins).
7. Perform a penetration with wings level through the cloud (115mins).
8. If a single cloud is large and clearly identifiable and the cloud is continuing to develop, make a reciprocal turn while ascending by ~1000ft (-3C in temperature) and repeat the cloud penetration several times (150mins).
9. If the cloud is not large or discrete, then proceed successively to the next visible cumulus cell, and repeat the penetrations at approximately 0C for a 10minute interval. Perform reciprocal turn while climbing by intervals of -3C and repeat 10minute runs (150mins).
10. Continue 8 and/or 9 as time permits (250mins).
11. Finish with a profile ascent from minimum permitted altitude to FL200 or 1000ft above highest cumulus tops (whichever is higher) at 1000ft/min.
12. Transit to Cranfield and land (300mins).

Note) – target clouds should be continuing to develop – look for rising cloud tops and solid, sharp-edged cloud boundaries. If red echoes show on the aircraft radar, or cloud top is decreasing, or cloud becomes heavily glaciated (diffuse boundaries) then move on to next cloud

DATE: 18/5/06

ICEPIC (SW APPS).

FLIGHT NO: B200

INCLUDE:

1. An assessment of the flight.
2. Summary of the weather conditions.

Overall, an excellent flight. Cumulus cloud conditions (base & tops, location) were much as forecast, being present over the areas flown (N. Cornwall & Devon; and along 250° - 070° radial from/to Chilbolton radar). Winds were generally WSW'ly at levels surface to FL 200, 25 kts increasing to ~60 kts at FL 200. A line of 'growing' Cu was 'worked' along N. Cornwall / N. Devon, generally along WSW \rightarrow ENE'ly ground track, where small Cu initially, became moderate then well developed (but with little glaciation) progressively in the E/ward direction. A full vertical 'stack' along this axis at differing heights, followed by a second stack with fewer levels was flown (see below). Thereafter, 2 runs ENE towards Chilbolton radar & 1 run away from the radar were flown for comparison with ground site data.

The cumulus activity gradually lessened during the sortie (as seen in vertical extent) and progressively from the West as somewhat more stable air invaded ahead of the next frontal system. An increase in Ci/Cs at high level above the aircraft, again from the West, was apparent in time.

After T/O from Cranfield at 0931 and a transit at medium level to the Bristol Channel, a profile descent FL 200 \downarrow 50' (ending just N. of Cornish coast, $\sim 50^{\circ} 36' \text{N}$, $5^{\circ} 00' \text{W}$) was made. Thereafter, the following runs were made:

- ⊙ Run 1. 100' / 1500' ($\sim 500'$ below C. Base), heading ENE, then reciprocal WSW.
- ⊙ Run 2. FL 070, Freezing level, heading NE', then ENE.
- ⊙ Run 3. FL 080, Temp $\sim -3 \rightarrow -4^{\circ}\text{C}$, heading WSW.

- ⊙ Run 4, FL 090, Temp -6°C , ENE'wards
- ⊙ Run 5, FL 100, Temp -7°C , WSW'wards.
- ⊙ PROFILE P2, FL 100 \downarrow 1500' @ $\sim 1000'/\text{min}$, over S. Bristol channel, finishing over land (H. Devonport) Cornwall.
- * Run 6, 1500' (below c. base), ENE'wards
- * Run 7, FL 070 (in freezing level) WSW'wards.
- * Run 8, FL 110, ENE'wards. Reposition to start.
- * Run 9, FL 110, inbound 070° Radial \rightarrow CHILBORTON (finishing just to E of radar).
- * PROFILE ^(Mini-) P3, FL 110 \downarrow FL 070 ($\sim 1200'/\text{min}$)
- * Run 10, FL 070, outbound 250° (freezing level)
- * Run 11, FL 070, inbound 070° (").

Run 11 ended W. of CHB, then the aircraft returned to Cranfield, landing at $\sim 1420\text{L}$.

The De-iced Temperature sensor went to full-scale after about 3 hours into flight & remained v/s thereafter; this affected the HORACE computation/display of wind data (several comparisons were made with Flight Deck ^{derived} wind data). The Non-De-iced Temperature worked well, throughout. No significant ice-build up on external A/C sensors was noted. Other instrumental data seemed fine.

A 'classic' ICEPIC study which should yield an extremely useful and valuable Cu cloud / convection dataset.

~~DK~~ 18/5/06.

Mission Scientist's Log

[ICEPIC] AREA A (+CHILBOLTON)

Flight No **B. 200**.....

Date **18/5/06**.....

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0923					Start Taxi Cranfield. [011] [006]
0931					T/o Cranfield. 6/8 Cu, clear above.
0934		3000	310°		h/b cloud 2800'. 8ft turbulence in Cu.
0936		FL070			Cloud tops above here, still in cloud.
		FL084			General tops here, occ'l higher Cu tops.
					<small>Sky water content 6-8000' (water in windscreen)</small>
0938	TRANSIT	FL090	240°		How level at FL090
094710	*		260°		In cloud at FL090, ice columns seen on GPI.
094800		In cloud			Some water in this now, some ice.
094810		Out of Cu cloud.			FL ~ 10000'.
095420		→			Now at FL 200. Above general Cu tops at this level
		NOTE: First part of profile ascent from Cranfield			
		UP to 720 mb (+5C)			IN STRAT (Too HIGH). TEMP TRACE (T)
		✓ Problem with Airspeed			wake; OK above this level OK now (720 mb)
01148	P1.0	FL200	230°	S112; A12.0 N W	Start P1. WIND 240°/30 m/sec. (230°/30 m/sec Capt)
	(Captain pass)				
	Looking at Cu this building.				Cumulus now developed over Devon/Cornwall to S (increasing tops as head ENR along Cu "train").
					Much less cloud (smaller Cu/Sc) over B. Channel & to west
					Generally ~ 3/8 Cu (various stages of development)
					1/8 Ci above (low). TR of this Ac/Sc layers over water.
					[1000' / min descent]

Camera
⊕

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.200**.....

 Date **18/5/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
101910	P1.0	13400	SW	50° 54' N 4° 36' W	Passing 13,400'. (Profiling along N. Cornwall coast - keeping clear of cloud.)
		(Good)	Cu echoes from		lands end - main Cu activity over land (Cornwall/N Devon)
102358	Interrupt P1.0	8000'		50° 41' N 4° 48' W	Turning ↗ to avoid profiling thro cloud. sub-tropical.
102650	Restart P1.0	8000'	335°	50° 48' N 4° 36' W	Resume P1.0 (heading NW).
102951	Interrupt P1.0	5000'	334°	51° 00' N 4° 42' W	Interrupt P1, turn ↘
103112	Restart P1.2	5000'	207°		Restart P1.0 wind 220°/16 m/sec (in turn)
1034		2350'			Wind 223/20 m/sec (N. Cornwall Coast)
10355		1200'			Layer Sc now above & to SW. Hazy/Misty at low level.
10381	END P. 1.2	80'	203°	50° 36' N 5° 00' W	End P1.2 at 50' climb. Sea
1040					cloud base over land ~ 2000' - 2400'
					Setting up next run
104355	Restart P1.0	1500'	061°	50° 42' N 4° 30' W	Start P1. (500' under C. Base). Towards Brantable
104530					Rain on windscreen. Will repeat 500' under cloud (reciprocal for CCN).
105323	END R1.0	1510'	076°	50° 54' N 3° 36' W	End R1.0 Turning ↘
105507	START R1.1	1510'	265°	50° 54' N 3° 42' W	Start R1.1 WIND 220°/11 m/sec.
105840					ppm on screen. More ppm ahead at this level. Cloud tops on this run (CPI C. Physics)
110430					Wind 225°/2 m/sec.
11051	END R1.1	1500'	240°	50° 42' N 4° 30' W	End R1.1 Climb to FLO70.
110607					Into cloud or climb.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.200**.....

 Date **18/5/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1110	→	Cu tops	up to ~7000 ft & up to 10000' Recent higher		Manoeuvring before starting Run 1 or FLO70 (~freezing level) along same orientation SW → NE
111228	Run 2.0	070	046°	50°36' N 4°36' W	Start Run 2. 1 st cell coming up 30 sec, the 2 nd cell WIND 235°/23kts, then 3 rd cell (from radar).
111443					Out 1 st cell - Temp -1.3° C.
111535					Lots of rain on windscreen (2 nd cell)
111625					Tuning 30° R for next cell. Still in 2 nd cell.
111700					Clear cloud (end 3 rd cell)
111725			→		Into 3 rd cell Temp -1.8° 238°/22kts/sec.
111815					Turn into next cell ↓
		Next cloud tops ~10000' & building.			End
111930	R2.	FLO70 070	093°	50°54' N + 0 W	End R2. Manoeuvre & climb 1000' for -3 to 4 hrs.
					General cloud tops ~
112229	R3	FLO80	273°	51°0' N + 0 W	Start R3 [Ice Columns here (CPI)]
112345					Mod rain on windscreen [Temp ~ -4 C]
112415					Clear of cloud now [WIND 238°/22kts/sec]
112600					Enter cloud now.
112613					Mod rain on windscreen
112653					Out of cloud.

Active Cell ahead now

Mission Scientist's Log

~~Heathrow~~
~~10:45 pm~~
~~1/1/06~~

Flight No **B 290**

Date **18/5/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112745					Into next cell (big one! partial red centre)
112800				→	Mod/Heavy rain
112843					Again Mod/Heavy rain
112910					Out of cloud, heading ↓ for next cell. Temp [5.5°]
~ 113015					Entering next (smaller) cell (tops lower of this one) smaller ev (in queue) ahead to progress SW'wards.
113125					Rain here.
113208					In cloud tops.
113430				→	CPI - heavy now.
113440	R3	F080		5030m 4°24'W	End Run 3 at F080 [Temp 0°] [-3.5C] (at end)
					Climb 1000' (~3°C) for next run.
113725	START R4.	F090	336	5042 4°15'W	Start R. 4. at F090 [Temp 6.3] [wind 205/24 m/sec].
113920					Entering cell (top ~ 12000')
114012				→	Entering cell
114050					Out cloud.
114125					Enter next cell. Some ice here (CPI & E. Physics)
114245					Clear now.
114459					Enter next cell.
114526					Heavy rain here.

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B** 200

Date 18/5/06

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1147					Clear cloud, Ci invading from W
114720	4.0				End R4
114803	5.0	FL100	200°	51° 6' N 3° 42' W	Start Run 5 Temp [Passport] WITH TAT!
1150	→				Management [CPT probe in last cell]
					Temp -7.2°C Wind 225° / 15m/sec
115249					Out cell. In East of string of cells ahead. (General cloud tops ~ FL100) Ocul tops higher
					Thickening Ci overhead as heading SWwards.
120720			←		In cloud
120548	END RS.0	FL100		50° 30' N 4° 48' W	End Run 5. (1006mb)
120654	P2.0 start	FL100		50° 30' N 4° 48' W	Start Profile P2.0 ↓ 1000' / min
121135	Inter P2.0	5000'	295°	50° 42' N 5° 12' W	Interrupt P2 at 5000' (1006 mb)
121305	Start 2.1.	5000'	714°		Restart P2.1. ↓ 1500' @ 1000' / min
121440	END P2.1	3400'			Interrupt P2.1 (ATC)
121517	Start 2.2	3400'	155°	50° 36' N 4° 54' W	Resume P2.2
					Ahead (along N. Devon coast)
121650	END P2.2	1500'			End P2.2 Manage before start run under cloud (~500' below C. Base).
12175	Start P6.0	1500'	095°	50° 30' N 4° 45' W	Start R 6.0 below cloud.
121910			→		Head to N. coast & continue run under under cloud (or closer to coast) ✓

122100

Rain on screen; trying to stay ~50' under C. Base

Mission Scientist's Log

[9°C]

Flight No **B 200**.....

Date **15/5/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
122240					Now on N. side of heavier rain (with lower c. base)
1223	R6.0	1500'	053°	50° 42' N 4° 24' W	Temp +9°C ; Wind 230°/18m/sec
122505					Rain on windscreen. Heavy rain to start (SE) (Bodmin Moor)
123009	R6.0	1500'		51° 0' N 3° 48' W	End R6. Climb to FL (N Freezing 070 level)
123241	START R7.0	FL 070	300°	51° 0' N 3° 54' W	Start R7. at FL070. (Thicker Ci Cs above)
123328					Into cloud. (mainly in c. tops). Chasing heading to pass thro ^{more} Ci cells on this run (several times).
123545					Several Ci tops at FL070 ground here Ocul tops to FL100+ (Heavier echos ahead)
1238			→		Enter next cell complex.
124000					Mod / light rain on windscreen.
124032					" " (again).
1241.					[TAT to OFFSCALE ; Turn on heater heater again]
124458	END R7.0	FL070	198°	50° 30' N 4° 18' W	End R7 at FL070. Climb to FL110 (track of R7).
1246					6/8 Ci Cs above now.
					Setting up for next run SW → NE
124914	START R8.0	FL110	051°	50° 30' N 4° 24' W	Start R8.0 TAT heating Temp still u/s FROM NAT OK though. DI probe
125120			→		Into cloud ; Many columns here (CPI)
125225			→		Out of cloud WIND 230/25m/sec.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....200.....

 Date 18/5/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125315					Into next cell.
125350					Mod rain now (on windscreens)
125416					Out of cloud now. - line of larger Cu to stratus (to RSE)
125600					Into cloud & out (~10 secs)
					Extending low 8.0 from N. Devon to become 1 st of approaches to Chulbolton (radar to) at this level (FL110).
125815					Still in cloud.
125900					Out of cloud for few minutes (J/W to be zeroed)
130100					Cloud report ^{5.6 N} 3.6 W. Cu generally up to FL100 actual tops higher 4/8 Ci / Cs above.
130320	R 8.0	FL110	136°	^{0.1} 51° 06' N 3° 06' W	Message to Chulbolton to be o/h at 1323
				4/8 Cu	Clouds less 'energetic' here (18. tops 7-8000' actual tops 10000')
130809	END R 8.	FL110	148°	50° 54' N 02° 42' W	End R 8.0. [Wind 230/25 m/sec]
131000	START R 9.	FL110	085°	50° 54' N 2° 30' W	Start R 9.0 AS ults to CHB.
1314		→			Above Cu field at this height generally actual Cu to ~ FL130 (spread to NE).
131844					9 ults → 7 ults (larger Cu) tops up to ~12000' taken picture here (2)
131924	R 9	F			o/h Chulbolton now!
131932	END R 9.	FL110	(080)	^{0.1} 51° 06' N 01° 18' W	End R 9. (just ^{past} o/h CHB), turn ↓
13				clear	Clear above; 6/8 Cu below gen tops 7000'
					Descend to FL 070 for next turn (Approx FL)
					AFTER passing CHB AT FL110.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 200.....

Date 18/5/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132358	P2.0	FL110	248°	51° 06' N 1° 18' W	Start Profile P3.0 (~1200'/min)
132522				→	Into cloud now
132605	→ FL083			→	[Columns on CPI here]
132640					Rain on Windscreen
132710	END P3.0 START R10	FL070	245°	51° 00' N 1° 36' W	End P3.0 / Start R10. [HERE Collect WIND TEMP U/S]
132757					Out cloud now Flightdeck [WIND 230/37kt] WINDS 120/12kt
				←	Camera fix ③, ④, ⑤ [Stbd, forward aspect.]
133030					Out of cloud now.
133125				→	Cu tops now lower ahead on this run
133210					Ci / Cs thicker to W on this run. + layer cloud to W thickening.
1335.					Camera star ⑥ of Cloud ahead ⑦
133624					Cu Cells ahead just passing Photo ⑧
133647	Good			Drifts) etc	Pass thro cell } 39nm from CHB.
133702	ISOLATED Cu.			[c. Physics]	Out of cell. [Temp -0.2°C]
134237	END R10	FL070		50° 48' N 2° 48' W	End R10. More Ci / Cs above (SAME CU STABILISATION) Sc/Ac cloud here (generally more "messy") at this end, also some layers
134510	START R11	FL070	101°	50° 54' N 2° 36' W	Start R11 at FL070.
1347				→	Ths' cloud tops now.
1352.					Photos ⑨, ⑩ on this E' hand leg.
1353					C. Tops up to FL090 ahead (stabilising here).
135514	END R11	FL070	090	51° 01' N 01° 30' W	End R11. (to W. CHB). Descend & RTB
135620					Into cloud.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date:18/05/06	Operator: KT	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:11:50	121	0.07	270	0												FL200 start P1	
10:12:55	147	0.06	270	0												FL190	
10:13:57	197	0.06	270	0												FL180	
10:15:32	195	0.06	270	1												FL170	
10:16:20	124	0.06	270	0												FL160	
10:17:42	274	0.06	270	1												FL150	
10:19:09	246	0.07	270	1												FL140	
10:20:20	273	0.06	270	3												FL130	
10:21:18	333	0.06	270	3												FL120	
10:22:07	203	0.06	270	0												FL110	
10:22:48	350	0.06	270	1												FL100	
10:23:30	325	0.06	270	3												FL090	
10:23:59	389	0.06	270	3												FL086 interrupt P1.0	
10:26:00	232	0.07	270	3													
10:26:50	246	0.07	270	3												FL086 continue P1.1	
10:27:20	279	0.07	270	8												FL080	
10:28:16	242	0.07	270	9												FL070	
10:29:15	222	0.06	270	20												FL060	
10:29:57	249	0.07	270	10												FL055 interrupt P1.1	
10:31:12	186	0.07	270	10												FL055 continue P1.2	
10:31:49	201	0.07	270	10												FL050	
10:33:03	226	0.07	270	10												FL040	
10:34:13	419	0.07	270	90												FL030	
10:35:10	354	0.07	270	90												FL020	
10:36:24	416	0.07	270	100												FL010	
10:37:09	445	0.07	270	100												FL005	
10:38:12	439	0.08	270	100												End P1.2 at 50FT	
10:39:38	357	0.08	270	100												FL010	
10:41:30	369	0.08	270	90												FL020	
10:43:00	418	0.07	271	100													
10:43:53	380	0.07	271	80												Start R1 (500FT below cloud)	
10:46:00	329	0.08	271	40													
10:47:00	307	0.08	271	40												1	
10:49:00	395	0.08	271	80		1.00	800	0.07	800							1	
10:51:00	443	0.08	271	80		0	800	0.007	800							1	
10:53:00	358	0.08	271	50													
10:53:23	315	0.08	271	50												End R1.0	
10:55:10	340	0.08	271	50												Start R1.1	
10:57:00	332	0.08	271	70													
10:58:10	740	0.08	271	90		1.5	0	233	1000							1	
10:59:00	446	0.08	273	90		0.5	0	108	1000							1	
11:00:06	377	0.08	273	80				116	1000							1	
11:02:00	287	0.08	273	60		0	0	0	0								
11:03:16	351	0.07	273	40		0.5	800	0.007	1000							1	
11:05:09	318	0.07	273	30												End R1.1	
11:06:09	2633	0.06	295	1000		3	400	283	1000							1	Into cloud

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date:18/05/06 **Operator:** KT **DRS Time:** 08:30:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 2 of 2**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:08:00	116	0.08	311	8		0	0	0	0							FL070	
11:10:00	154	0.07	312	2000		14	0	0.007	1000								
11:12:00	9584	0.06	386	4000		12	400	8.337	1000						1		
11:12:28	14584	0.07	455	5000		132	325	291	1000						1	Start R2 at FL070	
11:14:25	2035	0.06	602	4000			400		1000						1	1 st cell	
11:15:20	219	0.07	607	4000		120	625	2125	1500						1	2 nd cell	
11:16:20	4416	0.06	727	1000		17	300		500						1		
11:17:40	1326	0.06	807	4000		51.5	550	366	500						1	3 rd cell ISOL graupel?	
11:19:00	14465	0.07	873	4000		58	125	25	500						1	End R2	
11:21:00	283	0.07	921	8		0	0	0	0							FL080	
11:22:30	8915	0.06	936	4000		132	600	16400	500						5	Start R3.0 at FL080	
11:24:00	13656	0.07	1043	4000		6.5	100		500						5		
11:26:00	5517	0.06	1062	4000		398	725	6991	1500						5	Some large drops too	
11:28:00	10915	0.07	1166	4000		236	775	2100	2000						1	Some ice	
11:30:00	294	0.06	1277	1000		146	275	416	275						8	Mix drops, ice	
11:32:00	821	0.06	1392	4000		378	575	1950	1000						1	Some ice	
11:34:00	6312	0.06	1447	4000		687	650	10958	650							Ice, drops, needles	
11:34:30	11453	0.07	1493	4000		453	750	6216	1500						5	End R3.0 Drops & ice too	
11:37:29	3159	0.06	1518	2000		0	0	0	0							Start R4 at FL090	
11:39:00	9150	0.07	1569	5000		494	325	25	400						7	Graupel?	
11:40:20	14716	0.06	1621	6000		501	775	2391	800						11	Some plates/graupel needles	
11:41:30	1790	0.08	1650	1000	237	450	3533	16291	1500						5	Some snow and ice	
11:45:00	5247	0.06	1698	500		372	400	3308	2000						11	Some snow/needles	
11:47:00	217	0.07	1776	5		0	0	0	0								
11:48:00	207	0.06	1776	0		0	0	0	0							Start R5 at FL100	
11:48:30	9612	0.07	1839	5000		154	275	366	1500						11	Some snow/needles	
11:49:26	14184	0.06	1876	6000		327	550	116	2000						11	Some snow/needles	
11:51:30	14306	0.06	1928	1000		125	400	17416	2000						5	Some 8, 7, 11	
11:53:30	780	0.06	1971	800		38	400	183							7	Mix	
11:54:40	5033	0.06	1990	4000											4	Mix Dendrites?	
11:56:00	240	0.07	2015	5		0	0	0	0								
11:56:30	5212	0.06	2031	4000		123	200		200							Mix	
11:57:50	13711	0.06	2052	5000		251	300	1818	300						8	Mixture some graupel/ice	
11:59:00	225	0.06	2080	5		0	0	0	0								
11:59:26	12016		2114	4000		340	200	330	200						8	Mix	
12:02:00	457	0.06	2122	1000		0	0	0	1000						3	Mix	
12:03:00	1937	0.06	2131	2000		70.5	750	26785	1500						5	Mix, mainly columns	
12:04:00	1993	0.07	2134	4000		1752	725	28950	725						5	Some ice, snow	
12:05:47	262	0.06	2179	0		0	0	0	0							End Run 5.0	
12:06:54	262	0.06	2179	5		0	0	0	0							Start P2 at FL100	
12:07:55	289	0.06	2179	4		0	0	0	0							FL090	
12:08:55	288	0.06	2179	0		0	0	0	0							FL080	
12:09:50	359	0.06	2179	5		0	0	0	0							FL070	
12:10:43	540	0.06	2179	200		0	0	0	0							FL060	
12:11:48	1427	0.06	2179	900		0	0	0	0							FL050 P2 interrupted	
12:13:12	709	0.06	2179	100		0	0	0	0							P2 continued	
12:13:27	313	0.07	2179	200		0	0	0	0							FL040	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date:18/05/06	Operator: KT	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:15:33	436	0.07	2179	80		0	0	0	0							FL030	
12:16:24	511	0.07	2179	100		0	0	0	0							FL020	
12:16:50	492	0.07	2179	80		0	0	0	0							P2.2 end at FL017	
12:17:47	457	0.07	2179	20		0	0	0	0							Start run at FL017	
12:20:00	464	0.07	2179	80		0.5	500	100	500						1		
12:22:00	332	0.07	2180	80		0	0	0	0								
12:23:30	383	0.07	2181	90		12	175	2583	200						1		
12:25:00	450	0.07	2181	90		8.5	800	550	800						1		
12:27:00	420	0.07	2182	50		0	0	0	0								
12:28:00	372	0.08	2182	70		1.5	600	16	1500						1		
12:30:09	376	0.07	2182	80		0	0	0	0							End Run 6	
12:32:00	183	0.07	2187	20		0	0	0	0								
12:32:36	191	0.08	2187	90		0	0	0	0							Start run 7 at FL070	
12:33:30	7404	0.07	2197	1000			300	66	1000						1	Some ice/graupel	
12:36:00	305	0.08	2204	9		3.5	400	141	1200						5	Some graupel/snow and ice	
12:38:00	533	0.06	2252	100		102	725	11800	2000						3	Graupel/ice/needles too	
12:39:00	8690	0.06	2273	3000		168	800	9750	1000						3	Some needles	
12:40:30	11952	0.07	2333	5000		602	660	1700	1500						3	Some needles/ice	
12:42:00	7827	0.07	2500	3000		518	550	2391	550						3	Some graupel/ice	
12:43:30	9648	0.06	2540	4000		1862	500	8400	2000						3	Some ice	
12:44:57	308	0.06	2577	0		0	0	0	0							End R7 at FL070	
12:47:00	245	0.07	2577	5		0	0	0	0								
12:49:14	288	0.06	2577	5		0	0	0	0							Start R8.0 at FL110	
12:51:25	1184	0.06	2582	2000		358	450	46000	450						5	Some aggregates	
12:53:30	6107	0.06	2602	3000		1236	700	73608	750						5	Some aggregates	
12:56:00	292	0.06	2624	5		0	0	0	0								
12:56:52	4323	0.06	2639	2000		1127	775	74508	800						5	Some aggregates	
12:58:10	4635	0.06	2664	2000		136	750	12991	800						5	Some aggregates	
13:00:00	301	0.07	2872	0		0	0	0	0								
13:02:00	295	0.06	2672	5		0	0	0	0								
13:04:00	287	0.06	2674	3000		549	625	28991	625						5	Some aggregates	
13:06:00	314	0.07	2690	0		0	0	0	0								
13:08:05	295	0.07	2690	4		0	0	0	0							End Run 8	
13:10:00	357	0.07	2690	5		0	0	0	0							Start Run 9 at FL110	
13:12:00	331	0.07	2690	4		0	0	0	0								
13:14:00	453	0.08	2690	5		0	0	0	0								
13:16:00	370	0.08	2690	5		0	0	0	0								
13:18:00	432	0.08	2690	5		0	0	0	0								
13:19:24	347	0.08	2690	0		0	0	0	0							End Run 9 overhead Chilbolton	
13:21:00	4377	0.08	2690	5		0	0	0	0								
13:23:00	446	0.08	2690	7		0	0	0	0								
13:23:49	446	0.08	2690	3		0	0	0	0							Start P3.0 from FL110	
13:24:39	377	0.08	2690	3		0	0	0	0							FL100	
13:25:29	3085	0.07	2690	5000		348	750	9591	2000						5	FL090	
13:26:29	6955	0.06	2742	1000		158	500	5093	2000							FL080	
13:27:10	8023	0.07	2775	5000		66	775	775	2000						5	FL070 end P3.0 start Run 10 some drops	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B200**Date:**

18/05/2006

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B200_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B200_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	19/06/06	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B200 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B200_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	0 142121	Problems running this but Manually edited o/p file
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B200 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use, in order of preference, - if a calibration exists after the flight date, then the file that is closest in time to it, - or the most recent calibration file prior to the flight date. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	N 21/06/06	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL03052006.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B200_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B200_mfdX','pmsdata:B200_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	21/06/06	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 2 secs manually added
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B200_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:B200_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	21/06/06	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		YES. OK agreement with Nevzorov LWC
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		Nevzorov has lots of flag 2 data where TWC is zero/3 in cloud
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B200**Date:**

18/05/2006

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B200.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B200.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B200.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B200.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B200_seadas.dat iii) exit	19/06/06	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 65380 blocks read/written No bad reads
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B200 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B200_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data N j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: N l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	19/06/06	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files. Not required Not required
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B200 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B200		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B200

Date:

18/05/2006

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B200_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B200.nc]	21/06/06	As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B200.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B200.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B200_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary	21/06/06	

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:B200*.* outdir:B200_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir" In CLOUD_PHYS:[BROWN.PMSZIP]

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B200**Date:**

18/05/2006

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B200_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B200_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B200_FFSSP.raw B200_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_b200_rawffssp.zip		Raw data sent to BADC from FAAM
3) Transfer SEADAS B200.dat file from CD/DVD to PC 4) Zip up file on PC (B200.zip)		
- rename B200.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_b200_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_b200_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_b200_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	1	2	3	4	5	REMARKS
			24.08						
			20.36	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
START	OF	RUN ϕ		0.17	0.30	0.50	0.70	1.07	S
				241	290	258	335	1137	D
				270	261	236	286	221	B
				2379	2338	2337	2725	2331	R
				995.5	995.7	995.7	995.6	995.5	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

SLOW TO SAMPLE
15 MIN TOTAL

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	18/05/06	Flight	B200	log pages
Operator(s)	James Bowles	Campaign	ICEPIC			
Departure	Cranfield	Arrival	Cranfield			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	08:07
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	18.3°C	Ch 17	18.1°C	Ch18	17.6°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	08:08
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290.3	Cold	292.3		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	08:15
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	NOT FITTED					
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot			Cold		
Target heating						•
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud	2/8 cu	Precip	none		
	Surface	dry	Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	08:59	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.54	Cold	295.34
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	43.96	35.15	38.11	41.21	42.49

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	
						09:22

Flight #	B	Date	Operator(s)	log page	2	of	2
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys

08:21	prefli		Ch.16 u/s to start	
08:33	"		Ch.16 power cycled + now working	
09:33			Takeoff	
09:40ish	Trans		In cloud	
09:48	"		Out of cloud	
10:06	"		Land-sea	
	P1		Descent to msa	
10:26			P1 int & turn about	
10:29:51	P1		Interrupt & turn	
10:35			Under layer sc	
10:38			P1 end	
10:39			Under small cu patchy + manouvers	
10:43:55			R1.0 500ft below scattered cloud	
10:53:23			Eor1	
10:55:07			R1.1 same height	
10:58			Precip	
11:05			Eor + cimbing	
11:05			Into cloud	
11:12:28	R2		7000ft in cloud/ in and out smallish cu	
11:15			Precip	
11:19			Eor2	
11:22:29	R2		8000ft ? -4C in & out cloud	
11:34:			Eor	
11:37:25	R3		9000ft -6C in/out cloud	
	R4?			
11:48:03	R5		10000ft in/out cloud	
12:05:48			Eor5	
12:06:54	P2		Descent to 500ft below cloud gen clear sky	
12:16:15	Eop			
12:17	R6		Below cloud some manouvering	
12:30:09	Eor6		Climbing to 0C	
12:35?	R7		In cloud	
12:44:57	Eor7		Climbing to -9C	
12:48			In clearish skies some cirrus above	
12:49:40	R8		Starts clear	
12:51			In cloud -still ci above when between cells	
13:04			Cu below, ci above not in cloud	
13:08:05	Eor8		Turning	
13:10	R9		FL110 towards chilbolton cu below,patchy ci above.	
13:17			Unbroken Cu below , clear above	
13:19:32	Eor9		Broken cu (7/8) again below clear above	
13:23:58	P3		Descent to 7000ft	

13:25 in cloud

13:27:10 R10 incloud

13:28 patchy ci above and patchy cu below between main cells

13:32 mostly clear air with above situ. Only occasional cells

13:39 thicker ci above

13:40 skipping cu tops below

13:42:37 oer10 & turning

13:45:10 r11 entering cloud

13:47 out of cloud, broken cu below, ci above

Flight #	B	Date	Operator(s)	log page	3	of	3
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>			Sys	

13:55:40 eor11 ci thinning at this point & Descent into cloud
 13:57 ci very patchy in/out cu
 14:15 below cu
 14:26 MARSS PC 11 sec fast

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 200** Date: 18th May 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	n
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y	Racks:	
FWVS	y	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI	N
“ Red	Y		
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	n
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	n
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
DEIMOS	n	IR Camera	n
ARIES	n	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	n	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	y
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B200

Date: 18th May 2006

Instruments

1. DITM went to full scale several times during flight, this affects many derived parameters
2. FFC iced over several times despite demister on
3. Outboard video signal occasionally intermittent
4. TWC – status light came on at temperatures less than –25C
5. Heimann total water alarm sets occasionally, usually in cloud

Aircraft

Satcom Calls

1 x Met Office (Chilbolton)

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B200:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	NO log taken - replaced by post flight auto cal removal
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Sep 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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